
A Study of Digital India Programme Opportunity & Challenges in India

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ABSTRACT

Fast internet access is being made available in rural regions as part of the Digital India strategy, which aims to deliver digital capabilities throughout the country. There will also be fewer long lineups at banks and businesses. The primary goal of Digital India is to enable the nation's economic growth by offering an increasing number of services to the public online. By doing this, high-speed internet access would be made available in all parts of India, from rural to urban areas, enabling individuals to access all services from the comfort of their own homes. In order to make it easier to identify every Indian and enable the use of numerous government programs from a single card, the government has completed a number of significant projects under Digital India, including connecting Aadhar cards to bank accounts, PAN cards, mobile numbers, and life insurance services. But it is a big challenge to implement it all over India, there are many obstacles in the way of its successful implementation Ex: - Digital illiteracy poor infrastructure low internet speed lack of coordination between various departments issues related to taxation cyber security etc. for this a lot of dedication and effort will be required by all the departments of government and private sector. If the facility of Digital India will reach all the citizens of India, then this scheme will open many new opportunities for the citizens. This study of mine explains the opportunities and challenges faced by the Digital India campaign,

especially based on the opportunities and challenges faced by DBUs, e-RUPI, the 9 pillars program of Digital India.

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Introduction:-

On July 1, 2015, Narendra Modi, the Indian prime minister, unveiled the Digital India. initiative. The Goal of Digital India is to Make An Increase in the Amount of Services Available Online in The Nation. The Department of Finance Services, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, and National Health Authority have all established digital services under this umbrella. We shall learn more about how Digital India contributes to the country's development as we do more research.

Under this scheme, high speed internet facility will be provided everywhere in India from small village to city, with the help of which people can do their work online A total of 75 digital banking units were launched in the country on 16 October 2022 to make this facility accessible to every nook and corner of India through Digital Banking. Through this scheme Self Service Zone will work 24/7, through which all facilities like passbook printing tax bill payment credit debit card account open check deposit, access to internet banking etc. will be available online, all will be done with the help of EKYEC. Under the e-RUPI scheme, the amount is given to the beneficiaries directly in the bank account itself. This digital service has been launched by the Department of Finance Services, Minister of Health and Family Welfare and National Health Authority.

Key behind Digital India:-

1. An all-encompassing program, Digital India includes all divisions.
2. The following are the main driving forces behind Digital India: 1. Indian Talent (IT) Information Technology (IT) + INFORMATION TOMORROW.

LITERATURE REVIEW:-

Midha (2016): Although there are numerous obstacles to overcome before adopting Digital India across India, he claims that the program is a fantastic idea for the country's future development. However, if used improperly, it could fail. It has the potential to be the best failure for India if properly carried out. To boost the knowledge economy, he advised all citizens to collaborate. (1)

Singh (2015): He provided a brief review of India's digital economy. He looked at the program's framework as well as how Digital India might affect the country's IT industry.

In his opinion, the campaign was successful and should be finished with revisions. India has to improve its labour laws.

A number of projects have been launched as part of this initiative to support rural development and the agriculture sector, as well as to focus on the empowerment of rural Indian women, according to Gupta and Arora (2015), who investigated the effect that Digital India had on India's rural sector.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:-

Secondary material from journals, periodicals, the Internet, and research papers is the foundation of this work of mine.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:-

1. Investigate the Digital India.
2. Vision Learn about his nine digital India pillars.
3. Investigating the Digital India Unit for Banking
4. Investigation of Digital India's E-RUPI Program.

HYPOTHESIS:-

HO:- Digital India programme has no significant role in 9 Pillars programme in India.

H1: Digital India plays as an important role in 9 Pillars programme in India.

HO:-Digital India program has no significant role in digital banking Unit Scheme (DBUs) in India.

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VISION OF DIGITAL INDIA:-

The following are the three main pillars of the digital India vision:

1. Infrastructure as a free service for all citizens:

- A. Every gram panchayat would have access to a high-speed internet connection.
- B. Having a bank account will allow for individual participation in the financial and digital industries.
- C. Citizens will get digital identity.
- D. The focus will also be on safe and secure cyber space.
- E. Private entities shareable on the public cloud.

2. On-demand governance and services:

- A. Making financial transactions electronic and cashless.
- B. Availability of government services on online and mobile app.
- C. Government services to be digitally transformed to improve doing business.
- D. All civil rights will be accessible in the cloud.

3. Digital Empowerment of Citizens:

- A. A public program for digital literacy will be put into place.
- B. All digital resources to be made universally available.
- C. The cloud will house all official certifications and documents.
- D. The existence of digital services in Indian languages.

Nine Pillars for Digital India

First Pillars - Broad band Highways:-

- i. Broad Band Highways will be implemented in rural areas through the Department of Telecom Corporation.
- ii. Rural Broad Band Highways intended to cover Gram Panchayats.

iii. The emphasis will be on amending the laws to allow for the effective development of board band highways in urban and rural regions.

iv. Growth The National Information Infrastructure (SWAN, NKN, and NOFN)

v. would be implemented within two years through the integration of a program. Informational websites and mobile apps will be created.

Universal Mobile Connectivity is one of the second pillar:

i. Expand network coverage for ubiquitous mobile connectivity.

ii. Universal mobile connectivity will be made available from the Department of Telecom Inquiries facility

Third Pillars of the Public Internet Access Program:

i. One of the third pillars of the Public Internet Access Program is the National Rural Internet Mission.

ii. For the purpose of the Public Internet Access Program, the Post Office will be transformed into a Multi Service Centre.

Fourth Pillar: electronic governance Using technology to change government:

i. The transactions will be improved with the use of IT.

ii. Business Facilitation.

iii. Interference between the departments of tracking and online applications.

UIDAI, Payment Gateway. Mobile Platform, and EDI Facility will be Available.

iv. Integration of Services and Platform.

v. Electronic databases: There will be access to all databases and information in electronic form.

Workflow automation will be implemented in the government.

E-kranti, the fifth pillar, is the electronic provision of services:

Education-e-education technology:

- i. All schools are now connected to the internet via broadband.
- ii. Free Wi-Fi is available in schools and institutions (2.5 Lac.).
- iii. There will be a program for digital literacy.
- iv. Develop and test pilot MOOCs massive open online courses.

Health -e Healthcare

- i. Online medical records will be preserved online.
- ii. A medical consultation service will be offered online.
- iii. Now that the supply of medications is
- iv. A Pan-Indian Exchange for patient data will be offered.

IT for plan

- i. Making decisions for GIS.
- ii. The mode project for the national GIS mission.

Technology for security:

- i. Emergency mobile services.

Technology for farmers:

1. Ordering input online.
- ii. Online cash loans and mobile banking for relief payments.

Financial inclusion technologies will include the following:

- i. Mobile banking will be made available.
- ii. A micro-ATM program will be developed.
- iii. Postal service/CSCS.

Technology for justice and security:

- i. Centre for national coordination on cyber security.
- ii. A facility for e-police and e-courts will be made available

Information for all, the sixth pillar:

- i. Online notifications for special events or programs to citizens.
- ii. Documents that house information online:
- iii. Platform for open data.
- iv. Information is accessible to all people.
- v. taxation and incentives, lastly.

Target NET ZERO imports for the seventh pillar, which is electronic manufacturing.

- i. taxation and incentives
- ii. Remove economic and cost disadvantages.
- iii. Developing skills.

8th Pillar: IT for Jobs

- i. The government intends to teach 1 crore students from rural and small-town areas for the IT industry.

Nine Pesos for Digital India

- i. Growth the National Information Infrastructure (SWAN, NKN, and NOFN)
- ii. Would be implemented within two years through the integration of a program. Informational websites and mobile apps will be created.

Digital Banking Units (DBUs):-

Digital Banking Unit has been opened in 75 districts of India on 16th October 2022. This Digital Banking Unit will be open 24 hours a day, people will be able to transact their money and open an account, apply for credit or debit card. And will be able to do all those things. which are done in the bank. In future, digital banking units have now been launched in all the states of the country, through which people living in villages and small town will be able to make money transactions with the help of this.

75 Digital Banking Units have been opened in 75 districts in the last six months.

Through this scheme, all the work that we do in the bank will be able to be done through digital bank units, those who do not have laptop and mobile, they can go to the digital banking unit and do banking related work now for any work. No need to queue and wait for hours.

1. Under digital banking units, there are 11 public sector banks, 12 private sector banks, and 1 small finance bank unit.
2. ICICI Bank has opened digital banking units in many cities.
3. Digital banking is used by 26% people in India followed by 22% in Ireland, 21% in Singapore use DBUs.

Utility of DBUs:-

1. Savings account can be opened.
2. Balance check can be done.
3. Print Passbook.
4. Fund can be transferred.
5. Investing in fixed deposits can be done.
6. Applying for credit and debit cards.
7. Pay taxes and bill.

E-RUPI:-

E-Rupi is like a digital voucher, the person receiving this benefit will get it on the phone in the form of QR code & SMS, through which the amount will be directly transferred to their bank account this E-Rupi digital payment facility has been created with the support of both the (DFS) Department of Finance Services and the NHA (National Health Authority) and is operated by the National Payment Corporation of India. It can be redeemed at any specific centre where it will be accepted and that too without any internet banking/debit/credit card and can be availed by just a simple phone call through mobile app.

1. NPCI has currently contracted up with more than 1600 hospitals for E-Rupi where E-Rupi will be paid.

2. The goal of e-Rupi is to introduce digital currency to India, but it is not a true currency; rather, it is a system of social service vouchers.

Opportunities in the Indian digital economy include

1. **Digi Locker**, It is also known as Digital Locker, is a virtual safe where anyone may store their documents, such as grade reports, Aadhar cards, PAN cards, driving licenses, and voter identification cards. From the Google Play Store, an Android phone can download the Digi-locker app.

2. **My Gov.in**: The objective of this policy is to encourage citizens to work closely with the government.

3. **E-sign Framework**:- Signature is an opportunity to digitally sign documents by the Aadhaar holder using an online service.

This opportunity has been given by:-

1. Legally valid signature facility.
2. Easy to implement.
3. Privacy
4. Secure online service.

4. **Swachh Bharat mission mobile app**:-Swachh Bharat Mission Application has been launched to track cleanliness coverage in real time which can be downloaded in any Android and Window Mobile. This app has been launched by Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation. Beneficiaries for Mission Grameen Programme the number of domestic toilets built for construction can be seen.

5. **E-Hospital**:-So far 420 hospitals have been added to the e-hospital, in which almost all the major hospitals of the country are connected, through which the patient does not have to stand in long lines, he can put his number online. More than 4000000 people have taken the benefit of e-hospital so far.

6. **National scholarship portal**: Through this, you can get information about all types of scholarships on a single platform, all facilities are provided online on this portal.

7. Bharat Net:- Through this program, residents of rural and distant areas will be able to get broadband services at competitive prices. It is the nation's largest rural broadband connectivity project. Around 2.5 million by 2021. There are 6 lac gram panchayats. Under this program, villages are included.

8. DBUs:-

1. Balance check
2. Print Passbook.
3. Fund transfer.
4. Fixed deposit Investing.
5. Loan application.
6. Applying for credit and debit cards.
7. Pay taxes and bill.
 - *Empower digital services.
8. Robust digital banking infrastructure.
9. Promote transparency.
10. Promote financial Inclusion.
11. Economy of a country.
12. Banking system robustness.
13. Direct benefit transfer.
14. Digital transaction.
 - Small business owners.
 - Village business - digital.
15. Cyber security awareness.
16. Cost-effective.
17. Safe and secure.

9. E-RUPI:-e-Rupi can be tracked whether voucher is used or not, e-Rupi will keep the beneficiaries information completely confidential e-RUPI has the potential to support small businessmen to take benefits of government schemes Digital India plan can increase GDP by \$1 trillion by 2025.

Challenges of Digital India:-

1. Cyber security
2. Acceptance among customers
3. Need for infrastructure development.
4. Digital divide
5. Connectivity remote area
6. High level of Digital Illiteracy
7. Exchange of information.

Conclusion:-

The 9 Pillars of India program run by the digital India program has contributed significantly to the development of India and with the use of DBUs, all the work of the bank has become easier, through this we will no longer have to stand in long queues and print the passbook opening of savings account. In check balance fund transfer work a lot E-RUPI is a kind of voucher, it can be redeemed at any specific centre where it will be accepted, that too without any internet connection and without any mobile Through this app, we found in our research study that digital India is very important for the development of India by this all the work is done online and the use of Digital India is very beneficial especially for those places where the bank market is far away, we can now save our documents in DG Locker for life time and digital banking units in India. The scheme which has been implemented on 16 October 2022It will make the life of the citizens of India very easy because through this all the transactions will be digital but implementing it all over India is a very challenging task.

Suggestions:-

Making the Digital India program a success is a very challenging task, there is still a need for change in India to make digital India. Digital India plays an important role in empowering citizen, but it is difficult to inform. How to avail the facility online of this program to make it successful, there is a need to run a wide awareness program, especially people living in rural and remote areas need to be informed about the benefits and to inform them how to get their benefits.

The recommendation is as follows:

1. Making digital divide available across all of India.
2. The private sector should be supported in building infrastructure in rural areas.
3. To develop cyber security skills, cyber security courses should be started at the graduate level.
4. People must be informed that they can use the E-Rupi and Digital Banking Unit services.
5. Demands extensive digital literacy in India
6. In order to disseminate knowledge about Digital India, Common Service Centers must be established throughout India.

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